

Towards AI-driven multidimensional polarimetric imaging for advanced tissue diagnosis

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Polarization-based optical imaging techniques have received significant attention for their potential in biotissue analysis, including cancer detection [1]. In particular, tissue polarimetry has emerged as a powerful imaging tool for label-free and nondestructive tissue analysis, leveraging light polarization properties to detect abnormalities. Accurate identification of tissue types is crucial for pathologists to ensure precise diagnosis and effective treatment. Polarimetric measurements produce multidimensional datasets, comprising at least two spatial coordinates and four components of the Stokes vector for each spatial point. Manually analyzing such complex data is labor-intensive and time-consuming. To address this challenge, AI and machine learning (ML) models offer an efficient solution by processing high-dimensional data and extracting meaningful features at significantly higher speeds without compromising accuracy. In this paper, we explore the application of AI/ML techniques for analyzing and classifying tissue types using 6D polarimetric data. Furthermore, we conduct a comparative analysis of various ML approaches to evaluate their performance in tissue classification.

Formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded (FFPE) blocks of human breast tissue obtained from Biobank Borealis (Oulu, Finland) were scanned using a custom-built polarimetric imaging system. The system utilized a supercontinuum laser (Leukos Ltd., France) as the light source, with specific probing wavelengths selected via an acousto-optic tunable filter (Leukos Ltd., France). A wavelength of 640 nm was used for imaging. In the illumination arm, the linearly polarized light was converted into circularly polarized light using a quarter waveplate and then focused onto the sample. The remitted light was collected using a 100× objective lens and analyzed with a Stokes polarimeter (Thorlabs Ltd., USA). Spatial sample scanning was performed with an XY translation stage, covering 8 × 8 mm area at a resolution of 20 μm. The obtained set of images has been annotated using the reference to a conventional histopathological analysis performed by a professional pathologist.

Fig. 1. (a) Conventional histological image of a tissue sample obtained from a microscopic image of stained slices. Representative polarimetric maps measured from unstained, unsliced tissue blocks: (b) degree of polarization (DoP) and (c) V Stokes parameter (Q and U parameters omitted for brevity). (d) Tissue classification result using the trained SVM model, where green represents adipose tissue and blue indicates fibrotic tissue.

Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Random Forest (RF) models were employed to analyze the obtained datasets and classify them into two tissue types: adipose and fibrotic. To optimize model performance, we systematically tested various configurations of SVM and RF parameters. For SVM, we evaluated different kernel functions (linear, polynomial, and radial basis function), and regularization control (C) parameter. For RF, we explored different minimum leaf sizes. The optimal parameter combinations were selected based on the minimum mean square error criterion and used for further model training and validation across different sample sets. To evaluate model performance, we analyzed accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and loss plots for both training and testing datasets. As expected, increasing the number of training samples improved classification accuracy. Our results indicate that RF may provide better accuracy on smaller datasets, while SVM tends to outperform RF as the training dataset size increases, providing the ultimate accuracy of 97.12%.

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